

TECHNIQUES WRITING LESSON PLAN (RPP)

Yayan Sudrajat

Lecturer of Indonesian Education Study Program
Faculty of Language and Arts
Indraprasta University PGRI Jakarta

yayan.sudrajat@unindra.ac.id

Abstract: Writing a Lesson Plan (RPP) can only be done if the lecturer has written a Semester Lesson Plan (RPS). The Lesson Plan is the smallest learning program that contains a plan for the delivery of a particular subject to plan the expected final ability (KAD). The formulation of the Lesson Plan format that will be made at least consists of the identity of the course, the expected final ability, learning activities, learning media, learning resources, and assessment instruments.

Keywords: Lesson Plan, Lesson Plan Format.

INTRODUCTION

According to Government Regulation Number 32 of 2013 which is an improvement of Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education System, what is called learning planning is the preparation of learning implementation plans for each learning content. The Learning Implementation Plan or RPS will then be developed by the lecturer and the parallel lecturer team of the same subject in the study program. The Learning Implementation Plan or RPS is in accordance with the mandate of the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 49 of 2014 and the Minister of Technology and Higher Education Regulation No. 44 of 2015 concerning National Standards for Higher Education.

The Lesson Plan or RPS is composed of at least consisting of;

1. Study program, name of course and code of courses that have been agreed on internally in universities, semesters, credits, lecturers;
2. Achievement of graduate learning in courses;
3. The final ability expected at each stage of learning to meet the achievement of graduate learning / learning objectives
4. Study materials tailored to the abilities to be achieved;
5. Learning methods;
6. Time is available to achieve competence at each stage of learning;
7. Student experience in learning is realized in the job descriptions that must be done by students for one semester;
8. Criteria, indicators and assessment weighting; and
9. List of references used.

RPP or Lesson Plan is the smallest unit or unit of learning program that contains a plan to deliver a certain subject or unit of discussion to achieve one KAD (Final Expected Competency). Learning Implementation Plans, hereinafter referred to as RPP, which means pieces of activities to achieve

a learning achievement. In other words, the RPP is a derivative of the RPS that will be used by lecturers in each face to face learning.

Learning or teaching according to Degeng (Hamzah, 2014: 2) is an effort to teach students. In another sense teaching has the stages of selecting, establishing, developing methods to achieve the desired teaching outcomes. The stages of selecting, establishing, and developing this method are based on available teaching conditions.

In achieving learning objectives there are several things that need to be considered such as how to organize learning, how to convey the content of learning, and how to organize interactions between existing learning resources in order to function optimally.

According Dimiyati and Mudjiono (2008: 11) learning can also be interpreted as activities aimed at teaching students. in another sense, learning according to Winkel (Sobry, 2013: 12) is a set of actions designed to support student learning processes, taking into account external events that contribute to a series of internal events that take place within the student. Degeng (Sobry, 2014: 12) defines learning as an effort to teach learners. Whereas according to Suparman (2014: 79) learning is a series of planned interaction activities between students and learning resources to produce relatively constant behavioral changes

So, learning is a stage of an activity that is planned in an effort to teach learners from those who do not know to know, from those who do not understand to understand, and from those who already know to know more. Learning with teachers is called Teaching. Experience in events is not learning if it is not intentionally designed to achieve certain learning outcomes, even though it can lead to learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

RPP /Lesson Plann

RPP or *Lesson Plan (Lesson Plan)* becomes a guideline for lecturers and students in the course of one stage of learning, one meeting or more, as a director to achieve an expected final ability. Philip Combs (Kurniawati, 2009: 66) states that the implementation planning of learning is a determination that contains components of learning systematically. Systematic analysis is a process of educational development that will achieve the goals of education so that it is more effective and efficient arranged logically, rationally, in accordance with the needs of students, schools, and regions (community).

The Semester Lesson Plan (RPS) of the lecturer's handle in the implementation of learning that is still macro, general, broad. For shorter lecturers, the RPS still needs to be elaborated and the description is in the form of Learning Implementation Plans (RPP). Thus, the RPS will be explained in the RPP. RPS to achieve the learning achievement of courses, while the RPP is to achieve one learning achievement or one planned / expected final ability. So, RPP is the smallest learning unit or unit that contains a plan to deliver a certain subject or unit of discussion to achieve a final ability.

The Lesson Plan (RPP) is a plan that describes the procedures and organization of learning to achieve a basic competency in several meetings that refer to content standards, graduation

standards and has been described in the syllabus. (Minister of Education Regulation No. 103 of 2014)

According to Niron (2009) learning planning projects what actions will be taken when carrying out learning activities. It is possible that the implementation is not exactly what was planned, because the implementation of the learning process itself is situational. However, if the planning has been carefully prepared, the process and the results will not be too far from what was planned.

In line with that RPP definition according to Sanjaya (2008) RPP as a planning program that is prepared as a guide for the implementation of learning for each learning process activity. So it can be concluded that the focus of RPP is about instructional activities to guarantee the quality of learning objectives (Instructional Goals) in each learning activity of a course that is taught by the lecturer.

RPP is carried out, evaluated, and followed up by each lecturer who teaches courses both in teams and individually. RPP is developed sustainably by paying attention to evaluation results, learning outcomes, process evaluation (learning implementation). The results of this evaluation will then be used, and to be studied to develop RPP.

Principle of Preparation of RPP

RPP is a micro curriculum whose effectiveness is influenced by its preparation. According to Abdul in (Azizah; 2015: 62) explains that the principles that are taken into consideration in the development or preparation of the RPP, as follows:

1. The competencies formulated in the RPP must be clear, the more concrete the competencies are more easily observed, and the more appropriate the activities - activities that must be carried out to form these competencies.
2. RPP must be simple and flexible, and can be carried out in learning activities, and form students' competencies.
3. Activities arranged and developed in the RPP must support and in accordance with the basic competencies that will be realized.
4. The implementation plan of the learning developed must be comprehensive and complete and to be clear about its achievements.
5. There must be coordination between the components of program implementation in madrasas, especially if learning is carried out in team (team teaching) or carried out outside the classroom, so as not to interfere with the hours of other courses.

In line with that Rusman (2012: 7) mentions the principles of RPP preparation as follows:

1. Pay attention to individual differences in students. The lesson plan is prepared by taking into account the differences that exist in students, including gender differences, initial abilities, intellectual levels, interests, learning motivation, talents, potential, social abilities, emotions, learning styles, special needs, learning speed, cultural background, norms, value and environment of students.
2. Encourage active student participation. The learning process is designed to be student-centered to encourage motivation, interest, creativity, initiative, inspiration, independence and enthusiasm for learning.
3. Develop a culture of reading and writing.

4. Provide feedback and follow-up in the form of reinforcement and remedial services
5. Linkage and integration. The RPP is prepared by taking into account the linkages and integration of SK, KD, learning materials, learning activities, indicators of achievement of competence, assessment and learning resources in a single learning experience.
6. Implement information and communication technology.

Practically in the preparation of RPP, a lecturer must have mastered how to describe the learning outcomes of a course into an expected final ability, how to choose material that is suitable with the expected final ability, how to choose alternative learning methods that are considered most appropriate to achieve the expected final ability and how to develop evaluation of learning processes and results.

RPP format and components

RPP and RPS actually made with consideration to make it easier to control the quality of the learning process and have no rigidity in its appearance. RPS and RPP of a college are adjusted to the needs of the college. RPP refers to the learning process standards which include the characteristics of the learning process, the implementation of the learning process, RPP is made to ensure the achievement of final abilities at each stage of learning, the components at each stage of learning become references for other components, such as learning activities, learning media, learning resources, and assessment instruments. The following is the RPP format:

Course Identity:

Meeting to :

Time allocation :

A. Expected Final Capabilities:Final

B. Materials Study :

C. Learning Methods :

D. Media / Tools :

E. Introduction Introduction Core /Presentation :

F. Assessment Instruments :

G. Learning Resources / References :

Preparation of RPP

1. Meeting to:

RPP is made to achieve a final ability in learning that can be achieved by one or more meetings.

For example: 1st Meeting

2. Time Allocation:

Allocation of time for each RPP is determined by the area / size of the subject / unit of discussion covered. Time allocation will depend on the SKS weight of the course.

For example: for educational profession courses that weigh 3 credits, face-to-face lecture activities in each meeting for 150 minutes. The activity is structured by giving assignments for 180 minutes and assigning students to study independently for 180 minutes.

3. Expected Final Ability (KAD)

The final ability that is expected to be formulated using operational work sentences, namely using only 1 verb or specific and observable behavior so as to facilitate it in implementing and measuring it. The final ability that is expected to be formulated clearly, completely and

compiled from a simple ability to a more complex ability both cognitive, psychomotor and affective and endeavored to be complete and complete (hard skills & soft skills).

The element of knowledge is equivalent to the Learning Content Standards in the DIKTI national standard (SN) that is mastering the theoretical concepts of certain fields of knowledge and skills in general and the theoretical concepts of specific sections in those fields of knowledge and skills in depth. While the elements of general skills contain meaning in accordance with the details of the elements of general skills specified in the SN DIKTI.

The skill element is possible to be added by the study program to add specific characteristics of the college to graduates who demonstrate work skills in fields related to study programs, methods or methods used in work ability, and the level of quality that can be achieved, as well as the process of achieving these results. The scope and level of skill must be equivalent to the scope and level of work ability listed in the description of the DIKTI CP, namely: Apply, review, design, utilize science and technology, or solve problems.

The attitude element must contain meaning in accordance with the attitude element in the DIKTI SN. The study program can add an element of attitude to add the characteristics of higher education to graduates or for study programs whose graduates need special attitudes to run certain professions. The formulation of the final ability that is expected to contain specific behavior, giving rise to a complete and clear double interpretation. Complete has meaning in accordance with the signs of the subject of learning, operational behavior, learning material, achievement conditions and success criteria. Obviously it means not allowing multiple interpretations or using operational behavior that can be observed, containing one behavior and can be measured.

Operational verbs that can be used to formulate operational behavior in the end result that is expected to be chosen by one of the words contained in each aspect of learning as follows:

1. Cognitive (Knowledge) Aspects

- a. Implementation (C3): implementing, implementing, using, conceptualizing determining, processing, demonstrating, calculating, linking, proving, producing, demonstrating, completing, adjusting, finding.
- b. Analysis (C4): Differentiate, Organize, Associate, Diagnose, Detail, Analyze, Detect, Link, Solve, Describe, Separate, Select, Select, Compare, Contrast, Describe, Divide, Make Diagrams, Distribute, Analyze, Sort out, Accept opinions.
- c. Evaluation (C5): Checking, Criticizing, Proving, Maintaining, Validating, Supporting, Projecting, Comparing, Summarizing, Criticizing, Assessing, Evaluating, Giving suggestions, Giving arguments, Interpreting, Recommending, Deciding.
- d. (C6) : Building, Planning, Producing, Combining, Designing, Reconstructing, Creating, Creating, Abstracting, Categorizing, Combining, Writing, Designing, Creating, Designing, Reordering, Collating, Summing up, Making patterns.

2. Affective Aspects (Attitudes)

- a. Receiving (A1): Asking, Selecting, Following, Answering, Continuing, Giving, Declaring, Placing
- b. Respond (A2) : Carry out, Help, Offer yourself, Welcoming, Helping, Visiting, Reporting, Contributing, Adapting, Practicing, Showing, Bringing, Discussing, Declaring to agree, Practicing
- c. Appreciate (A3) : Demonstrate, Implement, Express opinions, Take initiatives, Follow, Select, Participate, Merge, Invite, Propose, Distinguish, Guide, Justify, Refuse, Invite.
- d. Organizing: Formulating, Adhering to, Integrating, Linking, Linking, Composing, Changing, Complementing, Perfecting, Adjusting, Equalizing, Organizing, Comparing, Maintaining, Modifying, Organizing, Coordinating, Arranging.
- e. Characterization by value (A5): Acting, Declaring, Paying attention, Serving, Proving, Showing, Enduring, Considering, Questioning.

3. Psychomotor aspects (Motion)

- a. Emulate (P1) : Copy, Follow, Replicate, Repeat, Obey, Distinguish, Prepare, Imitate, Show.
- b. Manipulation (P2) : Rebuilding, Building, Doing, Implementing, Implementing Beginning, Reacting, Preparing, Initiating, Responding, Showing Using, Applying.
- c. Precision (P3) : Show, Complement, Refine, Calibrate, Control, Practice, Play, Work, Make, Try, 'Position.
- d. Articulation (P4) : Build, Overcome, Combine, Coordinate, Integrate Adapt, Develop, Formulate, Modify, Install, Dismantle, Combine, Combine, Reject.
- e. Naturalization (P5): Design, Determine, Manage, Create, Build, Create, Create, produce work, Operate, Do, Implement, Work, Use, Play, Overcome, Complete.

To formulate the ability of the end first known as special instructional goals. According to Suparman (2014: 163-170) Special Instructional Goals are also the basis used in preparing the test. Because of this, Special Instructional Objectives must contain elements that can give instructions to the compiler of the test so that he can develop tests that can truly measure the behavior contained within.

These elements are known as ABCD which comes from four words, namely A = *Aundience* is a student, B = *Behavior* is a specific behavior that will be raised by students after completing the learning process in the course, the behavior consists of objects and verbs. The verb shows how students do something chosen from c3-c6 taxonomy bloom revised edition. While objects are what students will do. C = *Condition* is a condition that means the limit imposed on a student when he is tested, not when he is studying. D = *Degree* is the level of student success in achieving this behavior. If the ABCD element formulated in a Special Instructional Objective can be exemplified in the following sentence:

"If given examples of personal competence, pedagogic competence, and social competence, students in the second semester of Indonesian education study program would be able to mention the competencies that must be possessed by professional teachers at least 90% correct "

Examples of minimal final ability formulation: Students are able to mention competencies that must be possessed by professional teachers.

4. Study Materials Study

materials can be obtained by describing more detailed topics that support the achievement of the main topics.

5. Learning Methods

This process is developed through a challenging, stimulating and fun approach method so that lectures run actively where among students there is an exchange of knowledge, experience and ability activities. There are many choices of learning methods that can be used in accordance with learning needs including learning models with Student Centered Learning (SCL) approach that is able to foster soft skills and not forget that the selection of this method is also to find out what abilities students can get.

- a. Small Group Discussion
- b. Role-Play & Simulation
- c. Case Study
- d. Discovery Learning (DL)
- e. Self-Directed Learning (SDL)
- f. Cooperative Learning (CL)
- g. Collaborative Learning (CbL)
- h. Contextual Instruction (CI)
- i. Project Based Learning (PjBL)
- j. Problem Based Learning and Inquiry (PBL)

6. Media / Tools

In the learning media consist of messages / teaching materials in the form of software to be delivered and a display device / hardware. This simple media can be a piece of paper, a poster, etc. Media is a tool used to distribute learning material / messages / information so that it can be seen, read, heard by students, such as pictures, charts, videos, animated films, power points. The selection of media should be adjusted according to the learning method chosen.

7. Core Learning Activities / Final Presentations

Learning activities are arranged to provide assistance to lecturers in order to carry out the learning process in a professional manner. This activity contains a series of activities that must be carried out by students in sequence to achieve the expected final ability. The implementation of this learning is a form of interaction between lecturers, students, and learning resources in certain learning environments. Effective learning according to sani (2013) consists of four steps; namely

- a. Preparation
- b. Submission
- c. Training
- d. Appearance

The four steps will be applied in learning activities starting from the introduction, core activities, and closing activities.

- a. Preliminary activities are the initial stages of activities that aim to prepare students to be mentally prepared to learn new knowledge, skills, and attitudes in order to generate

motivation and focus students to actively participate in the learning process. In preliminary activities the lecturer needs to convey the expected final ability after completing lectures and lecture material coverage. In the preliminary stage the lecturer also conducts apperception activities which is the initial checking of students and linking the real conditions in the community with the lecture material that will be discussed with the previous material, drawing pictures, playing videos. The duration of this preliminary activity is 5-10% of the total learning time.

- b. The core stage or presentation is the main stage in learning that contains descriptions, examples, discussions, or exercises about the material to be studied. This activity has a duration of 70-80% of the total learning time. This core activity contains various exploration, elaboration, and confirmation.
- c. Closing is the final stage of a lesson used to provide confirmation, summary, assessment, and follow-up on the material being reviewed. The duration of this closing activity is 5-10% of the total shopping time.

8. Assessment Instruments are

Appraisal carried out using an assessment instrument as a benchmark for achievement of abilities. Assessment of processes and products should be carried out with the principles of educative, authentic, objective, accountable, and transparent which are carried out *integratively*. The shape of the instrument with its assessment technique must be appropriate. The form of instruments that can be developed can be in the form of:

- a. The written test can be in the form of multiple choice, verbal, match up, etc.
- b. Oral tests are usually in the form of a questionnaire
- c. Performance test
- d. Assignment
- e. Observation
- f. Portfolio

9. Learning Resources / References Learning resources

are sources of literature or a collection of references in the form of books, journals, bloggers, and so on that are used as reference for learning related RPP. Writing a bibliography using the "APA" model

CONCLUSION

With the making of the RPP by the lecturer of the course and by the parallel lecturer team the courses are expected to be learning will encourage the growth of students' enthusiasm, motivation and confidence so that they can actively learn in a challenging, comfortable and fun classroom atmosphere. The RPP is prepared by providing sufficient space for the development of student initiatives, creativity, and independence in accordance with the talents, interests, physical and psychological development, and the student environment.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 32 tahun 2013 yang merupakan penyempurnaan dari Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 19 tahun 2005 tentang Sistem Nasional Pendidikan
Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Nomor 49 tahun 2014 tentang Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran atau RPS

Permendiknas No. 103 tahun 2014 tentang silabus.

Peraturan Menteri Riset Teknologi dan Pendidikan Tinggi Nomor 44 tahun 2015 tentang Standar Nasional Pendidikan Tinggi.

Tesis:

Dewi, Kurniawati Eni. 2009. Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Bahasa Dan Sastra Indonesia Dengan Pendekatan Tematis. Program Pascasarjana Universitas Sebelas Maret. Surakarta.

Books:

Anderson, L. W. dan D. R. Krathwohl. 2015. Kerangka Landasan Untuk Pembelajaran, Pengajaran, dan Asesmen Revisi Taksonomi Pendidikan Bloom. Terjemahan : Agung Prihantoro. Pustaka Belajar. Yogyakarta.

Dimiyati & Mudjiono. 2008. Belajar dan Pembelajaran. PT. Rineka Cipta. Jakarta

Dominika Niron, Maria. 2009. Bahan Pendidikan dan Latihan Profesi Guru dalam Jabatan Pengawas Sertifikasi Guru Rayon 11 Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta diakses dari staff.uny.ac.id/.../modul%20pengembangan%2.

Hamzah, B. Uno. 2014. Perencanaan Pembelajaran. Bumi Aksara . Jakarta

Rusman. 2012. Model-model Pembelajaran Mengembangkan Profesional Guru. Raja Grafindo persada. Depok.

Rustipa, Katharina. 2017. Rencana Pembelajaran Semester dan Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran. BP-Unisbank. Semarang.

Sanjaya, Wina. 2008. Kurikulum dan Pembelajaran KTSP. Kencana. Jakarta.

Sani, Abdullah, & Ridwan. 2013. Inovasi Pembelajaran. Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.

Suparman, Atwi. 2014. Desain Instruksional Modern Panduan Para Pengajar dan Inovator Pendidikan. Erlangga. Jakarta.

Sutikno, M. Sobry. 2013. Belajar dan Pembelajaran. Holistica. Lombok.

Sutikno, Sobry. 2014. Metode & Model-Model Pembelajaran Menjadikan Proses Pembelajaran Lebih Variatif, Aktif, Inovatif, Efektif, dan Menyenangkan. Holistica. Lombok.